

DEWEY'S PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR DEMOCRATIC EDUCATION IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: *Education is a powerful instrument for actualizing a nation's socio-political, economic, and cultural aspirations. The National Policy on Education 2013; provides the yardstick for assessing the nation's provisions for emancipating its citizens from ignorance and political instability. This paper therefore, analyses Dewey's educational philosophy vis-à-vis the Nigerian education system with a view to finding out how democratic principles reflected in Dewey's philosophy of education can impact on the Nigerian education system. From conceptual and logical analysis of the study, the researchers explored democratic values of equal access to educational opportunities, belief in intrinsic worth and human capacity to solve social problem, freedom of individual to hold ideas, and the role of schools to contribute to social change. Furthermore, the study discovered that inadequate funding of education, poor philosophical posture and failure to implement the national policy on education can negate the realization of policy objectives. The paper concluded that Dewey's philosophy of education can shape the Nigerian education system by entrenching democratic ideals of equal educational opportunity, learner freedom, and enhancement of individual capability to solve personal and social problems. However, issues of funding of education, implementation of educational policy and teacher training must be addressed. Based on the foregoing, the paper recommended that efforts should be made to fund education adequately, that teachers should be trained professionally, the curriculum content of education should be reviewed, and policy prescriptions should be implemented.*

INTRODUCTION

Education has always been associated with the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, and competencies for individual and societal

survival. For Amaele & Okere (2016), education is both a process and a product. As a process, it deals with producing capable human beings, and as a product, education activities and processes

Dr. Okere, Joseph Ejimogu and Dr. Obiukwu, Kingsley

anchor on the production of acceptable, self-reliant, dependable, effective, and efficient citizens. The product of education is the educated man who is a recipient of maximum awareness, knowledge, skills and attitudes which enable the individual to improve the quality of his life and that of his society. Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle have postulated on the aims of education. Socrates taught that certain fundamental principles were necessary for the survival of the state. These principles were specified as temperance, justice, courage, wisdom, and loyalty. Plato, belonged to the Athenian city state where the modern day democracy began. Athens practiced democracy, in which every citizen enjoyed the right to vote and be voted for; and the right of participation in the discussion and decision-making process in the general assembly. Plato, in his celebrated book “The Republic,” put forward a system of education based on what he considered the strengths of the Spartan and Athenian education. He proposed an ideal state in which social justice and social harmony were the dominant values. Justice was defined in terms of the duties and responsibilities which formed the obligations of the citizens to the state; and in which each man is contributing to the welfare of the society in that area where he had a natural talent. Aristotle, in his famous book, *The Politics*, contended that the role of education was to help the child realize the ideal pattern or the best of its kind, which is that of a full-grown happy adult. Happiness according to Aristotle, is a life of activity involving the exercise of the highest capacity that man has, that is; intellectual ability.

For Dewey, and other pragmatists, education is basically an art and the teacher should express

the highest concept of this art when he keeps education from becoming routinized and lethargic. As a social process, education should enable human beings to reason, understand, and adjust properly in their environment. In his scientific humanistic philosophy of education which is based upon experiential learning and experimental outlook to life, Dewey espoused how the scientific method of enquiry could help develop learners to acquire social intelligence for problem-solving. His philosophy of experience entails that learning should be by doing and that scientific method is central to education. It also implies that education should inculcate moral principles as well as democratic ideals in the learner. Dewey advocated a socially relevant education system in order to make learners active members of a democratic society. Dewey believed that democracy has the potential to nurture individual talents to the maximum benefits and utilization based on the belief that individuals have intrinsic worth and unique capacities to become intelligent human beings. He equally believed that each individual should be treated as an end and therefore, society should provide equal educational opportunity for individual self-fulfillment.

Nigeria has adopted democracy as a form of government, and as a social process; basing her education on democratic principles of freedom, equality and social justice. According to Okere (2021) education in Nigeria has undergone several stages of development from pre-colonial, post-independence, to modern period. The precolonial period witnessed an informal education system that was unstructured. In this system, the teaching method was traditional means of imitating the parents and elders.

Dr. Okere, Joseph Ejimogu and Dr. Obiukwu, Kingsley

However, the advent of the Christian missionaries caused a change in the traditional education system. The western education system introduced instruction in the three (3Rs) of reading, writing and arithmetic and religion as was necessitated by the demand for Christian teaching, messengers, court clerks and interpreters of the bible (Okere, 2022). This system of education was criticized for being too theoretical, elitist, and for neglecting the socio-cultural circumstances of Nigeria.

Consequent upon the hue and cry of this educational system, the Nigerian government under the auspices of the National Curriculum Conference of 1969, charted a new course for education in Nigeria. The deliberations of this conference gave rise to the birth of the first ever comprehensive document on Nigerian education tagged “National Policy on Education” which was formulated in (1977) with revisions in 1981, 1989, 1998, 2004, and 2013. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) education should equip the individual with necessary skills, knowledge and competence to live in society. Nwosu (2013) noted that the Curriculum conference recommended that education must at the primary and secondary school levels meet the present needs of the child and that of society, and that it should aim at preparing the child for adult life, higher academic achievement and excellence in education. According to the policy document, ***Nigeria’s philosophy of education is therefore based on the integration of the individual into a sound and effective citizen and equal educational opportunities for all citizens of the nation at the primary, secondary and tertiary***

levels both inside and outside the formal school system (FRN, 2013).

The National Policy on Education under the current 9-3-4 education system, made provisions for different types and levels of education, including basic education, senior secondary, and tertiary education. There are also special education, teacher education, and education services. Objectives of the various types and levels of education have been enshrined in accordance with the provisions of the national educational goals.

The aim of this paper is therefore, to analyze Dewey’s philosophy of education, vis-à-vis the Nigerian education system, with a view to finding out how Dewey’s philosophy of education can impact on democratic education in the Nigerian secondary school system.

Concept of Philosophy of Education

Philosophy of education refers to the process of philosophizing in education and the product of that activity that is, it is both analytic and speculative. It must be concerned with a critique of the philosophical assumptions of the existing educational systems and practice from the stand point of compatibility, consistency and adequacy in the light of the growing body of human knowledge. This is the analytic aspect. Philosophy of education is also concerned with developing a positive conception of what education ought to be in the light of as much information about man, society, and the universe as he can muster from all available areas of experience and knowledge. This is the speculative aspect of philosophy (Okere, 2021). Both the analytic and the speculative activities must be combined to make philosophy of education relevant to the needs of the Nigerian

society. In simple terms, philosophy of education refers to the use of philosophical tools, theories, and principles, and methods for the elucidation and solution of educational problems. (Aminigo & Nwaokugha, 2006). The main task of philosophy of education is the systematic and critical analysis, and clarification of concepts, issues and propositions in educational practice. It is the use of philosophical methods, instruments and theories to understand and find solution to educational problems.

Concept of Democracy

Education in Nigeria is said to be based on democratic principles. In Democracy and Education Dewey (1916) discussed democracy as an educational aim. He regarded democracy as a veritable tool for resolving conflicts in interests and values in a society. For Dewey, democracy is a moral and political agenda of schooling for resolving conflicts between political institutions and industrial arrangements. It can make contributions to the all-round growth of every member of the society. Dewey is also optimistic about the future of democracy in the education of the citizens. He regarded democracy as a unifying factor based on the principles and practices of democracy which he proposed throughout the educational system. He maintained that schools should be freely available to all from kindergarten to college. He further stated that school children should be trained to behave co-operatively, sharing with and caring for one another. Dewey believed that there is an intrinsic connection between the prospects of democracy and belief in the potentialities of human nature for its own sake. He believed that education can develop human capacities. Democratic freedom according to

Dewey is the cause of the fullest possible realization of human potentialities. He maintained that this capacity is not already formed and ready to be realized but if given the opportunity each individual can grow socially, emotionally and intelligently, so that they cannot only decide what is good for them but can pursue it.

From the foregoing, philosophy of democratic education can be summarized as follows: education should give every child the chance to grow up spontaneously, harmoniously and all-roundedly; the school system should be open to all on a completely free and equal basis without any discrimination on account of age, ethnic and social status; the conduct of the pupils shall be governed by themselves according to the social needs of the society; interest shall be the motive for all education; teachers will inspire a desire for knowledge, and will serve as guides in the educative experience rather than as task masters; scientific study of each child's development and scientific approach to problem solving; a broad-based curriculum in order to provide more experiences to the child; learning by doing that is, learning must involve action and should be based on problem-solving; learner freedom and the child's activities should be purposeful, stimulating, interesting and rewarding, (Okere, 2022).

Dewey's Philosophy and Nigerian Education System: A Reflection of Democracy?

Dewey is a pragmatic educational philosopher of the 20th century. The 20th century is pre-eminently the age of science and technology and human world dominated by material benefits or practical usefulness of any activity that is being

undertaken. Dewey's philosophy of education made growth and the development of intelligence the cardinal points of education. Dewey championed a more practical and experiential approach to education, emphasizing hands-on-learning and the importance of connecting theory with real-life experience. According to Dewey and other pragmatists, knowledge consists of experience that is processed and refined. Education is defined in terms of experience. He thought that the experience that is educative is the type that makes possible other experiences in future. This experience must be productive and must not be a limiting experience. His definition of education is the continuous reconstruction or reorganization of experience which adds to the meaning of experience, and which increases the ability to direct the course of subsequent experience. This definition has implication for the educational process. It means that aims and values emerge during reconstruction of experience, and this means that there is no fixed way to true education. Dewey sees educational aims as emergent and subject to change from time to time. This idea is supported by Ofoego (2016) when she observed that experimentalism is a fundamental element in the philosophy of Dewey which also is necessary for the building of self-reliant competencies and point to the scientific dimension of his work. Furthermore, education should enable the human being to be fairly adjusted to his immediate environment. He conceived the aims of education as the results of the problem-solving situations which arise during the activities of life. In this process, education is life-related and consequently, the ultimate aim of education should be growth into

greater knowledge and control over the environment. Also, the aim of education must be founded upon the intrinsic activities and needs of the person being educated in consideration of his peculiar learning styles and responses in a manner that recognizes flexibility of outcomes. The school is pivotal in the education of the child. Dewey postulated that the school is not only a part of the community but a community itself in which the child is to acquire the experience of group living and cooperative learning activity. He reasoned that the school cannot directly change the society but can reform it by helping the child with social intelligence to cope with complex social life. Dewey (1916) posited that:

When the school introduces and trains each child of society into membership within such a little community, saturating him with the spirit of service and providing him with instruments of effective self-direction, we shall have the deepest and best guarantee of a larger society which is worthy, lovely and harmonious.

From the foregoing, the school and the community should be mutually related in the pursuance of the same goals in the interest of the larger society. Realizing this educational philosophy, Dewey placed high emphasis on the role of the teacher who should know the psychological development of the child.

He believed that education should foster democratic citizenship, critical thinking, and the ability to solve problems. He advocated for a curriculum that is relevant to students' lives and that encourages them to become active participants in their own learning. For him, experience comes as a result of man's interaction

with his environment. The process of interaction raises some problems for man which has some impact on him. This impact will induce man to act upon it; or undergo the consequence. He further stated that knowledge is a product of the interactions of a living organism with its environment; the experience gathered from social living, processed by intelligence and applied for problem-solving. In this philosophy, intelligence is defined as the quality of problem-solving. We are intelligent or we have intelligence, only in so far as we handle our problems in scientific ways; the ability to think out and use ways and means of effectively resolving our present problems. This is the use of reflective thinking in our daily life. Dewey popularized reflective thinking method as the most scientific and the most effective method of problem-solving. Dewey (1963) emphasized the role of education as a fundamental method of social progress and reform and should involve the activity method. The activity method is a method of learning by doing where learners are involved in activity. From the foregoing, Dewey's educational philosophy is based on child-centered education where the needs and interests of the child should be taken into consideration.

For Dewey, educational aims must be based upon what is already present in the educational situation; and must not lie outside human activities. He viewed aims of education as consisting of orderly and ordered activities and one in which the order consists in the progressive completion of a process. Dewey believed that educational aims must be flexible, emergent and responsive to the situation at hand. He further stated that educational aims must be capable of

translating into a methodology which is activity-oriented arguing that an aim becomes useless unless it is capable of constructing specific procedures for its own test, correction and amplification. Dewey noted that educational aims must satisfy certain criteria. These criteria included: an educational aim must be founded upon the intrinsic activities and needs of the given individual; an educational aim must be capable of being translated into a method; it must suggest the kind of environment needed to liberate and to organize their capacities; and educators must be guides against general and ultimate aims of education.

From the foregoing, Dewey believed that the function of education is to enable human being access his experience within his environment and devise relative methods by which he can interact with his social environment for survival and growth. He regarded growth as the enlargement of the capacity to learn from experience and to direct future experience in a meaningful way. This idea was corroborated by Ozmon & Craver (1981), who maintained that education for growth is synonymous with education for the democratic society. They believed that the ideals of the democratic society establish the potent ground that is germane for growth, and that the growth of education should support and develop the ideals of the democratic society. In furtherance to this view-point, they espoused the role of intelligence in helping human beings to break the bonds of habit making it possible to devise relative alternatives that are more satisfying and desirable; arguing that growth, democracy, and intelligence are inclusive and related aims of education.

Education should also enable the human being to fairly adjust to his environment. Furthermore, for Dewey, the process and the goal of education are one and the same thing. Enoh (2009:107) notes that “the general aim of pragmatic education is the development of the learner’s intellectual ability, acquisition of vocational skills, democratic ideals and citizenship, the development of self-reliance and ability to cope adequately in a world of pressing problems”. According to Okoh (2003:172) “pragmatism stresses action and doing and maintains that imaginative theorizing must be supported and controlled by the outcome of active experimentation”. The philosophy of pragmatism emphasizes the need for education to meet the diverse needs, interests and aspirations of students through its child-centered curriculum. It also stresses scientific approach to problem solving, experimentation and inventions through results-oriented academic programmes. Dewey believed that philosophy must become a form of social and political criticism that is consummated in practice, doing and consequences. Right living is perceived by Dewey when the individual engages in a reflective and critical understanding of one’s purposes and activities.

Next, is democratization of the educative process. Man is social and interacts with his fellow human beings for a harmonious living and this makes social efficiency imperative in man. Through a democratic society, (Siddiqui 2009:53) noted that the individual “can fulfill his purpose and perfect himself”. Democratic principles and ideals are central in Dewey’s philosophy of education. He opines that democracy is a kind of community in which there

is maximum participation in the deliberation about all matters that affect the lives of those within the community and in the decisions that arise out of those deliberations. Maximum participation is a condition of human flourishing; the dignity of all people in shaping their lives through sharing and deliberations over their respective experiences and views of the world. Learners ends or purposes should shape the teaching and learning process; and those ends being to participate in the deliberations and decisions as far as is possible.

To realize the educational philosophy adduced above, Dewey laid emphasis on the method of teaching. Teaching methods recognized by Dewey are methods based on the child’s natural inclination and interests to learn and are able to solve the problem of the child. He advocated that the child is the center of the educational system and that the teacher should be experimental in his dealings and should not be the follower of established principles and fixed methods. Dewey believed that principles and methods of teaching should be forged afresh in the light of real-life situations. The principles that govern and determine teaching methods according to Dewey can be summarized as relation with life and principle of action or learning by doing. The first principle means that methods should relate to the child’s life, interests, desire, and inclinations. The second principle is the actual working of theories or facts and implies putting the child in the actual situation of learning through which he can apply his natural aptitude for doing and making things to study those situations intelligently and to solve them absolutely.

Teachers’ role in the Deweyan philosophy can be described as that of guiding and putting the child

in the real situation of his life, so that he might be able to understand his life's problems and thereby solve them. The teacher should inspire the child to follow the principle of learning by doing or learning through experience (experiential learning). As noted by Socrates, in Okere (2022) the pragmatist teacher wants his pupils to think and act for themselves, to do rather than to know, to originate rather than to repeat. The teacher should create a problem solving attitude in pupils. The teacher is not the authoritarian and fearful figure as presented in the traditional philosophies of Plato and Aristotle. The teacher is essentially an organizer and a moderator of the child's learning in Dewey's philosophy. Given his cultural experience and expert training, the teacher is assumed to be familiar with the psychological development of the child, with his individual needs and interests, and with what type of experiences that are of greatest use to him in the society. He is to select the learning tasks on the basis of the above, and arrange them in logical order according to the developing ability of the child. The teacher is thus, not a spectator but rather a participant in the learning activity, sharing experience with his students, encouraging such shared experiences among them, and fostering their problem-solving abilities and promoting the development of intelligence.

From the foregoing analysis, Dewey's philosophy can be summarized as follows: Students acquire the independent habit of solving problems, and this method makes the teacher become a member of the class and only plays the role of a facilitator of learning; functional education in which the ability to perform productive tasks is

more emphasized than education aimed at achieving ideological conformity; the practice of freedom and democracy in terms of learner-freedom to ask and answer questions and the teacher exercising authority in the classroom without being authoritarian.

Education for Aristotle should focus on developing the capacities of the individual to enable him to know the truth. The ultimate aim of education according to him is the achievement of the knowledge of the nature and the inner workings of the universe, so that the learner may consciously adjust himself to what is real. He posited that the educational process should aim at helping the individual learner to form habits, dispositions, and tendencies to search for the truth, to grab it, enjoy it, and use it in every aspect of his life. The foregoing postulations on education, point to democracy and set the stage for discussions on Dewey's philosophy and the Nigerian education system.

Education in Nigeria has transited from pre-colonial, post-independence, to modern period. It was observed that so many years after independence in 1960, Nigerian education was still operating a foreign educational pattern that did not address the needs of an independent sovereign nation. Fafunwa (1974) observed that the colonial government did not pretend to build a Nigerian nation through the instrumentality of education. For him, education was rather used as an instrument of disunity since no reference was made at all to unity, nationalism, patriotism or national consciousness in any of the school curriculum between 1843, when the first school was opened in Badagry and 1960 when Nigeria gained her independence. He believed that the widespread dissatisfaction and condemnation of

primary and secondary education in the country then by both literate and illiterate Nigerians gave rise to the call for a revision of the Nigerian educational system. The aftermath of this call, was the National Curriculum Conference which was held in Lagos in 1969. In his reaction to the proceedings of the conference, Uruakpa (2007) noted that:

It was not a conference for educationists only, it was necessary also to hear the views of the masses of people who are not directly engaged in teaching or other educational activities for they surely have a say in any decisions to be taken about the structure and content of Nigerian education.

Furthermore, in his views on the National Curriculum conference, Nwosu (2013) observed that the aims of the conference were not only to review old and identify new national goals for education in Nigeria at all levels, but also, more specifically to provide guidelines on what the system should be accomplishing with regard to: the needs of youths and adult individuals in our society; the socio-economic needs, values, aspirations and the development of the society and; the curriculum substance, the subject-content of the system which is the means to the goals.

Appraisal of the National Policy on Education in Relation to Secondary Education

The main thrust of this paper is on secondary education. The education system in Nigeria has a leaning towards the development of democratic principles. The philosophy of Nigerian education is couched on the development of the individual into a sound and effective citizen and the

integration of the individual into his community and the Nigerian society. Nigeria currently runs a 9-3-4 education system comprising nine years of basic education, three years of senior secondary education and four years of tertiary or university education. According to Njoku (2025) the broad goals of secondary education shall be to prepare the individual for useful living within the society and higher education. In specific terms, secondary education shall: diversify its curriculum to cater for differences in talents, opportunities and roles possessed by or open to students after the secondary school course; equip students to live effectively in our modern age of science and technology; develop and project Nigerian culture, art and language as well as the views and feelings of others, appreciate values specified under the broad national aims; and foster Nigerian unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in diversity. The nation's beliefs are that education is an instrument for national development and social change, it is to promote a progressive Nigeria and maximize creative potentials and skills of learners. Furthermore, education according to the document, must be qualitative, comprehensive, functional and relevant to the needs of the society. Idowu (2021).

The features of secondary school education include the provision of a comprehensive curriculum comprising core subjects designed to broaden the learners' knowledge and outlook, vocational (elective) subjects and non-vocational elective subjects. Secondary education has two tiers of junior and senior secondary education of three years' duration each. The junior secondary education which is now part of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) under the current 9-3-4

education system shall be both prevocational and academic. This reflects compulsory basic education at the secondary education level. The Nigerian education system is based on a functional direction of school children to meet their diverse needs and achieve academic excellence based on the principles of freedom, equality and justice.

The national educational objectives are anchored on providing a free and democratic society; a just and egalitarian society; a united, strong, and self-reliant nation; a great and dynamic economy and; a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens (FRN, 2013). Freedom in education means that the individual should be able to exercise self-control on passions, desires etcetera and the school should teach freedom by encouraging learners to air their views on issues especially those that concern them. They should be encouraged to choose and study subjects of their choices. The principle of equality in education would lead to giving each child the opportunity to develop to his maximum potentialities; recognizing individual differences and needs, providing free and compulsory (basic) education to all citizens; inculcating in the learners the spirit of fairness and ensuring there are employment opportunities for the citizens at the terminal stage of training or schooling. A strong and self-reliant nation on the other hand means that our education system should be strengthened to resist lowering of academic standards. These national goals translate to a strong, dynamic and vibrant economy that guarantees citizen's rights, democratic education, self-reliance and political participation. The ideals of the National Policy on Education are for citizens to be free, just and

to live in a democratic society. The implication of this provision is that the Nigeria education is founded on the principles of democracy. In furtherance to the above, the National Policy on Education stated that: life-long education will be the basis of the nation's educational process; educational activity will be centered on the learner for maximum self-development and fulfillment; universal basic education in a variety of forms, depending on needs and possibilities will be provided for all citizens; efforts will be made to relate education to overall community needs; and the education system will be structured to develop the practice of self-learning.

The National Policy on Education (NPE) further spells out in categorical terms, the national philosophy as well as the national educational objectives. The National educational philosophy is "based on the 'integration of the individual into a sound and effective citizen and equal educational opportunities for all citizens of the nation at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels, both inside and outside the formal school system (FRN, 2013). In this vein, Nigeria's engagement in education is aimed at achieving these goals: the inculcation of national consciousness and national unity; the inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society; the training of the mind in the understanding of the world around and the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of his society (FRN, 2013).The ideals of the National Policy on Education are for the citizens to be free, just and

Dr. Okere, Joseph Ejimogu and Dr. Obiukwu, Kingsley

to live in a democratic society. The implication of this provision is that the Nigerian education is founded on the principles of freedom, justice and equality.

According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN, 2013; in the National Policy on Education, the following sets of beliefs are stated; education is a tool for individual and societal development; functional education promotes progressive and united nation and education must be relevant, practical and comprehensive. Education is responsible for the inculcation of the right type of values, and attitudes for the survival of the individuals and the Nigerian society. The above set of beliefs indicate that possessing the right attitude is crucial to the development of an enlightened and educated citizenry. Education in Nigeria should aim at promotion of respect for the worth and dignity of the human person; sustaining faith in man's ability to make rational decisions; enforcement of moral and spiritual values in interpersonal relationship; encouragement of shared responsibility for the good of the society; enjoining respect for the dignity of labor and; promotion of emotional and psychological health of the citizenry. The educational aims and objectives presented above align with principles of democracy as enshrined in Dewey's philosophy of education.

To achieve the above aims, teachers are needed to demonstrate the subject-matter knowledge and the appropriate methodology in the teaching and learning process. Nwosu (2017) believes that the teacher should be responsible to the learners in the following areas:

- (i) State clearly the instructional objectives;
- (ii) Exhibit appreciable levels of integrity;

(iii) Facilitate conducive classroom environment;

(iv) Encourage and reward learner's positive performances;

(v) Provide flexible guidelines in place of erstwhile rigid classroom rules;

(vi) Promote interactive and participating classroom environment;

(vii) Shift from the pedagogical stance of perceiving teaching as an act of disseminating ideas and imparting knowledge to a process of inspiring, coordinating and sensitizing the learner to cross-fertilization of ideas.

Under the policy document, Nigerian government is to fund education, provide basic infrastructure and train teachers in order to achieve the educational objectives. According to Idowu (2021) the policy stated that the financing of education shall be a joint responsibility of the Federal, State/Local Governments and Private sector. Efforts shall be made to increase government investment in education, strengthen governance framework, create modalities to effectively track expenditure and monitoring as well as evaluation of service delivery on education. In addition, funds shall be provided at the government levels to provide camps for victims of natural disasters instead of converting schools as make-shift camps. A further consideration of the document reveals the curriculum contents expected to be implemented especially, at the Basic and Post-Basic educational levels. The development of appropriate skills and dispositions to cope with the variety of moral choices and decisions encountered in a technological and ever changing world. The provision in the Nigerian

education relates to Dewey's conception of aims of education.

However, (Nwosu 2013:174) averred that these objectives have not been met by the Nigerian education system. He lamented the ugly situation of Nigerian education when he said that: "Nigerian leaders have been remarkably honest and courageous in admitting that this country is like a 20th century version of Sodom and Gomorrah.... Its morals are in tatters...its discipline in shambles". He also lamented that in the present day schools, particularly in institutions of higher learning, respect for constituted authority has dwindled considerably. Attachment to social ideals and time-tested cultural values have shockingly plummeted. The educated Nigerian is still divorced from productive activities. The emergence of education as a tool for social mobility through the instrumentality of examinations and the issue of malpractice including teacher immorality and cultism in the education institution when considered as facts in themselves are testimonies of the ugly situation of Nigerian education. He concluded that these two phenomena represent the tremendous challenge towards repositioning education in Nigeria. Nwosu (2013) noted that education in Nigeria should cultivate certain value system in the learner. These value systems include work ethics, attitude to wealth, attitude to government and commitment to moral standards. Nwosu is of the view that these value systems will lead to the development of virtuous men and women who will be enterprising and committed to the development of the Nigerian society. He posited that Nigerian education should be based on shared responsibility for the common good of the

society. Common good of the society comprises human health, freedom, dignity, justice, equality of opportunities, political participation to mention a few.

According to Okoh (2003:242), Nigerian educational policy is still tied to the apron string of Europe. Nigeria does not have a clear perception of what education is and what needs education ought to fulfill within the Nigeria context. He believed that the underlying purpose of education in Nigeria today is either to turn the Nigerian into a "Black-European" or to enable him to imitate and acquire the material achievements and possessions of ex-colonial masters. Furthermore, the ideologies and manifest values espoused by formal education in Nigeria, are by and large not Nigerian but are rooted in the heritage and purpose of our ex-colonizers and are dominated today by the class biases of the ruling or elite sectors of Nigeria who are either completely de-culturized or have become cultural freak. The foregoing analysis has challenges and implications for Nigerian education.

Secondary Education Based Challenges in Nigeria

Secondary education has grappled with a lot of challenges ranging from the teaching methodology, teacher training, student indiscipline, and poor funding of education. Teachers are poorly trained to embrace the new methodologies in teaching and they are poorly motivated, resulting in poor student quality and inability to cover the curriculum of studies. Most teachers still use the traditional methods of lecturing and story-telling in their teaching and some of them are poorly trained to embrace new pedagogies in teaching. The curriculum of

studies in terms of structure and practice has remained stagnant. This poor posture reveals its inability to meet the expected changes in learning outcomes and educational standards. Students indiscipline behaviour is another factor contributing to poor quality graduates both at the secondary and tertiary levels. Nwosu (2017) believes that “this generation of students engage in brazen indiscipline-a situation that could lead to unbridled exposure of the student’s privacy and innocence. He noted that morality is in tatters and discipline in shambles. Poor funding of educational infrastructure such as human and material resources, laboratory, technical and vocational facilities, conducive classroom and hostel facilities, have become major features of Nigerian secondary schools. These are contrary to the indicators of quality education.

Furthermore, the Nigerian secondary education system does not reflect a life-long enterprise. The school leavers and university graduates are roaming the street in search of white-collar jobs. Also primary and secondary school leavers are not practically oriented and there is no room for problem solving and group learning experiences. Also, educational activities are not centered on the learner for maximum self-development and fulfilment. Egbokhare 2021; had decried the nation’s education system which he said was crafted without a sense of ideological and philosophical clarity. The result was high level of graduate unemployment. He also stated that three related issues affect the nation’s absorptive capacity. These issues are the lack of a culture of quality, employment status not based on meritocracy, and the incident of graduate unemployment. He suggested that education in Nigeria should be remodeled in the area of

existing curricula to align them with the realities of the Nigerian people, the nature of the Nigerian society; and the aspiration level of Nigerians. Without these factors, he believed that the education system would not be able to achieve authentic social and cultural needs of Nigerians.

Implications of Dewey’s Philosophy on Nigerian Education

Dewey’s philosophy has several implications for Nigeria education in the following ways:

Aims of Education: Education should be regarded as life itself as against preparation for life. It should help man to reason and face challenges as he may encounter in his environment and educators should be aware of the interests and motivations of children as well as the environment from which they come. Therefore, growth, democracy, and intelligence should be regarded as inclusive and related aims of education. Growth should reflect the enlargement of the capacity to learn from experience and to direct future experience in a meaningful way.

Emphasis on practical skills: An experimental approach to the study of democratic values and political process in Nigeria at all levels of the educational system. Schools should teach practical skills which students can apply in the real-world situations. Education should therefore, prepare students for life in the society by equipping them with relevant and saleable skills for the world of work.

Emphasis on Problem-Solving: A discerning approach to the development of political consciousness and issues in the country and the world at large. Education should enable students to solve problems and face life challenges. Schools should be places where

students analyze problems, evaluate alternative perspectives and implement the most effective approach.

Emphasis on Experience: A pragmatic ideological and humanistic philosophy framework, which should be taught in the educational system and should be made to be a way of life in Nigeria. Education should be based on experiential learning through which students acquire the skills for problem solving. In education, students should be engaged in hands-on-learning experience which makes possible practical application of theoretical knowledge to real life situations.

Flexibility and Adaptability: Inclusion of a pragmatic philosophy of democratic development in the Nigerian educational system. Teaching and learning process should be experimental whereby, new approaches and strategies should be used in teaching students based on their interests and needs.

Curriculum: An articulation of the curriculum which will reflect in all the subjects at the primary and secondary school levels of education, so as to develop critical thinking, scientific method of problem solving and co-operative or group living among Nigerians. School curriculum should be diversified and widened to provide more enriching opportunities to school children. This amounts to comprehensive education for secondary schools.

Democratization of Education. Nigeria needs to democratize her education system in order to leverage Dewey's democratic principles. Dewey's philosophy of education is a flexible and adaptable approach to problem-solving that relies on the practical application of ideas and

the importance of observable evidence. It encourages open-mindedness, critical thinking, and active engagement skills to solve societal problems. Education in Nigeria should adapt this philosophy for quality education and global competitiveness.

Conclusion

Education in Nigeria is an instrument par excellence for effecting national development. Dewey's educational philosophy can greatly impact on Nigerian education in reflecting its democratic ideals of effective citizenship, equal access to educational opportunities, inclusive education, faith in man's capacity to develop and exercise creative intelligence in shaping the future for problem-solving; reflective thinking and critical inquiry; and a school system that is socially relevant, such that it should contribute in making learners active members of a democratic society.

The underlying philosophy of Dewey lies on his belief that education is a necessity for life. It renews the individual so that he is able to face the problems encountered in his interaction with the environment. Dewey thought that education should not be regarded as the mere acquisition of academic knowledge but as a constituent part of life. Based on this belief, he regarded education as an art and the teacher's role is to express this consent of art by making sure that education is not routinized and lethargic. Dewey also believed that the individual needs society as a necessary part of his learning experience and that we must guard against the school treating academic discipline as different from life itself. In this manner, the school should provide the child with a conducive environment to learn about the community life. It is Dewey's belief that

individuals should be educated as social beings, who are capable of participating and directing their social life.

Nigerian education can leverage Dewey's educational ideas to promote its democratic practices. The policy statements in the National Policy on Education are well-grounded to realize national aspirations based on Dewey's philosophy, but it is more of mere statements of intention of what ought to be and not what is. Therefore, there is need to fully implement the provisions of the National Policy on Education, adequate funding of education, professional training of teachers both in subject matter knowledge and teaching methodology, constant revision of the curriculum content, and rebranding of national philosophy of education to ensure that it represents metaphysical and epistemological assumptions about man and his place in the universe; and the societal assumptions about values.

References

Amaele, S., & Okere, J. E. (2016). Philosophy of technology education in Nigeria: Past and present. *Universal Journal on Sustainable Developmental Research*, 13 (1), 160-161.

Aminigo, M., & Nwaokugha, E. (2006). *An advanced introduction to philosophy of education*. Zelta Research Consult

Dewey, J. (1916). *Democracy and education*. New York: Macmillian.

Dewey, J. (1963). *Experience and education*: Collier Macmillian.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations have been put forward that efforts should be made to fund education adequately; that teachers should be trained professionally in order to ensure that they become effective in the management of instruction; that the curriculum content of education should be structured in a manner that the learner takes charge of his own learning and at his own pace; that the learning environment should be made conducive by democratizing the teaching and learning process in a manner that recognizes the right of learners to choose how to learn and what to learn; and that learning experiences should be based on the interest and nature of the child and that the national philosophy of education should be rebranded to align it with Nigerian assumptions about life, knowledge, and values.

Egbokhare, F. (2021). Vanguard News <https://www.vanguardngr.com> Universities are last channel for national development retrieved 5/10/2025.

Enoh, A. O. (2009). *Introduction to philosophy of education*. Midland Press Nigeria ltd.

Fafunwa, B. A. (1974). *History of education in Nigeria*. George Allen and Unwin.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National Policy on Education*. NERDC Press.

Idowu, S. M. (2021). Forty years of PEAN and Nigeria's national policy on education.

Nigerian Journal of Educational Philosophy (NJEP) 32 (1), 306-307.

New Delhi, A.P.H. Publishing Corporation.

Njoku, M. U. (2025). *The Teaching profession in Nigeria.* Zobby Iheoma and Concept.

Uruakpa, J. A (2007). *Basic issues in comparative education.* Finbach Company Limited.

Nwosu, O. (2013). *The dynamics of Nigerian educational philosophy: Critical analysis and synthesis.* Osyora Nigeria Limited.

Nwosu, O. (2017). *Ethics and the teaching profession: correlation matrix and critical challenges.* Labyrinths Publishers.

Ofoego, C.O. (2016). *Philosophy of Education: Focusing higher institutions.* Wilderness Voice Press.

Okere, J. E. (2021). Basic education for national integration. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Philosophy.* 32, 172-174..

Okere, J. E. (2022). Equal education opportunity and self-reliance: The Nigerian Experience. *A publication of the Philosophy of Education Association of Nigeria (PEAN).* 33 (1) 159- 162.

Okoh, J. D (2003). *A critique of Nigerian philosophy of education. Philosophy of education: Concepts, analysis and application:* Design Prints Publishers.

Ozmond, H., & Craver, S. (1981). *Philosophical foundations of education.* Charles E. Merrill Publishing company.

Siddiqui, M. H. (2009). *Philosophical and sociological perspectives in education.*

Dr. Okere, Joseph Ejimogu and Dr. Obiukwu, Kingsley